

Organizational Management and Instructional Leadership of Private School Heads in Davao City

Asisclo E. Paguican

Abstract. The study unfolded to assess the relationship between organizational management and instructional leadership of Private School Heads in Davao City. This used a non-experimental descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher-respondents. The treatments used were Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of organizational management in terms of compliance and accreditation is oftentimes manifested, while inclusivity and diversity, technology integration, faculty and staff development, and curriculum alignment and innovation are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive; while the extent of instructional supervision in terms of instructional resources, assessment and evaluation, innovation and research were sometimes manifested; while, instructional coaching was rarely manifested, thus, moderately extensive. There was a significant correlation between organizational management and instructional supervision. All domains of organizational management regarding curriculum alignment, faculty and staff development, compliance and accreditation technology integration, and inclusivity and diversity suggest significant influence over instructional supervision. Future research may investigate the implementation of technology in instructional supervision and its potential benefits or challenges, which could be a fruitful avenue for research.

KEY WORDS

1. organizational management 2. instructional leadership 3. technology integration

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1. Introduction

Private schools have been experiencing notable trends in organization and management. These trends reflect the evolving needs and expectations of students, parents, and educators worldwide. One significant trend is the increasing emphasis on technology integration. Private schools are adopting digital platforms and tools to enhance teaching and learning, streamline administrative processes, and improve stakeholder communication. Another trend is the growing focus on diversity, equity, and inclusion. They are implementing policies and programs to address issues related to equity and access, recognizing the importance of preparing students for a globalized world. In the international scenario, organizational management has become an integral part of management reforms in public-sector organizations. Mimetic isomorphism is surprisingly compatible with processes of organizational learning and thus

does not inevitably compromise organizational development (Ansmann and Seyfried, 2022). Across many international contexts, designing and constructing architecturally different school buildings has become a key strategy in providing innovative learning environments designed to prepare students for work and life in the 21st century. Despite the global popularity of this strategy, research has highlighted persistent challenges associated with the transition to and occupation of innovative learning environments. Deppeler et al. (2022) explore the nexus between risk and innovation, reporting on data from a primary school in Australia built as part of one state government's Private Public Partnership initiatives. According to faculty members' opinions, Aydug and Agaoglu (2023) examine the mediation role of intentional organizational forgetting in the relationship between organizational learning and innovation management. The study's results showed statistically meaningful and positive relationships between organizational learning, innovation management, and intentional forgetting in higher education institutions with respect to faculty members' opinions. Instructional leadership in private schools within the Philippine educational system faces several significant challenges. One of the primary challenges is resource limitations. Many private schools in the Philippines need help with financial constraints, which can affect their ability to invest in quality instructional materials, professional development for teachers, and the maintenance of facilities. This challenge can hinder their capacity to provide a conducive learning environment. Private schools must compete with the public sector and need help attracting and retaining highly qualified educators due to differences in compensation and benefits (DeAngles, 2020). Private schools are working to create more inclusive environments that celebrate cultural diversity and provide equal opportunities for all students (Altun et al., 2022). Curriculum alignment is also a noteworthy challenge. Ensuring that the curriculum meets educational standards and the specific mission of the school can be complex. Balancing the need for innovation while adhering to regulatory requirements can be particularly challenging. Inclusivity and diversity are essential but challenging aspects of instructional leadership. Striving for inclusivity while maintaining affordable tuition can be a delicate balancing act. Many private schools aim to offer quality education to a diverse student population, but achieving this goal can be demanding. Like many educational leaders, private school heads in Davao City face various challenges related to organizational management in the context of instructional leadership. School heads often must make difficult decisions regarding budget allocation, teacher salaries, and facility maintenance while striving to provide effective instructional leadership. Teacher recruitment and retention present another challenge. Attracting and retaining highly qualified educators is competitive, as Davao City has a diverse education sector with numerous private schools. Private school heads must offer competitive compensation packages and professional development opportunities to secure and retain talented faculty, which can be complex (Real-Carillo et al., 2023). Curriculum alignment and adherence to regulatory standards pose challenges as well. Ensuring that the curriculum meets both government-mandated requirements and the specific mission of the school while promoting innovative teaching practices is a delicate balance. The changing educational landscape, with periodic curriculum and assessment framework revisions, demands adaptability and ongoing professional development for teachers and school heads. Additionally, issues related to inclusivity and diversity are significant. Striving for inclusivity while managing tuition fees and ensuring access to quality education for a diverse student population can be complex. School leaders must navigate this balance while

upholding the values of equity and social responsibility (Chang, 2022). Lastly, as in many places, the unpredictability of external factors, such as government policy changes, can challenge private school heads' ability to maintain effective instructional leadership while ensuring compliance with evolving educational standards. Thus, this study is conducted.

2. Methodology

Research methods encompass a range of techniques and approaches that guide the researcher in making informed decisions throughout the research process. They help ensure the study's validity, reliability, and ethical soundness. Quantitative methods, such as surveys and experiments, are employed when numerical data is required to test hypotheses, establish relationships, or measure outcomes. Selecting research methods also involves decisions about data collection instruments, sampling strategies, and data analysis techniques. These choices impact the quality and accuracy of the research findings. Researchers must rigorously plan, execute, and document their methods to ensure transparency and replicability, which are essential for building on previous research and advancing knowledge in a particular field.

2.1. Research Design—Non-experimental descriptive-correlational and predictive research designs represent essential methods in the field of research, each with its own distinct purpose and characteristics. Non-experimental research primarily focuses on observing and analyzing existing phenomena without manipulating variables. Descriptive research seeks to provide a comprehensive and detailed account of a particular situation, population, or event (Creswel, 2014). Correlational research, on the other hand, examines the relationships between variables, aiming to identify patterns, associations, or connections among them. It does not imply causation but helps researchers understand how changes in one variable may relate to changes in another. Predictive research design extends beyond describing and correlating variables. It involves developing models or theories to predict future outcomes or behavior. Researchers gather and analyze data to establish patterns that can be used for forecasting or making informed decisions. While these research designs serve distinct purposes, they share common advantages. They offer practicality, allowing researchers to study phenomena as they naturally occur, which is often the case in the social sciences. Non-experimental research designs are more ethical and logistically feasible when manipulation or experimentation is inappropriate or impossible. However, a limitation is the need for more control over variables, making it challenging to establish causal relationships. Non-experimental descriptive, correlational, and predictive research designs serve as crucial tools for studying organizational management and instructional leadership within the context of private schools led by heads of institutions. In organizational management, descriptive research helps provide an in-depth understanding of private schools' structural and procedural aspects. It allows researchers to document how decisions are made meticulously, resources are allocated, and policies are implemented. Correlational research, on the other hand, aids in identifying relationships between various management practices and educational outcomes, such as student performance or financial stability. By examining these correlations, private school heads can better comprehend the factors influencing their organization's success. Predictive research is invaluable for these leaders as it enables them to forecast future trends, assess

the potential impact of management decisions, and make informed choices regarding resource allocation and budget planning. In the realm of instructional leadership, these research designs serve a similar purpose. Descriptive research captures the intricacies of leadership practices, helping private school heads understand their roles and responsibilities in the teaching and learning process. Correlational research investigates how leadership styles and strategies relate to teacher effectiveness and student achievement. In this context, predictive research allows leaders to anticipate the outcomes of different leadership approaches, guiding them in making strategic decisions that enhance instructional leadership practices. These research designs equip private school heads with valuable insights and data-driven information to make informed decisions, improve their institutions, and foster effective organizational management and instructional leadership.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Private School Heads in the Davao City Schools area. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where a total of 60 School head respondents were taken randomly from Schools that surround the City. After being selected through randomization, respondents were notified both through online platforms and in-person, taking into account the availability of Wi-Fi connections. Additionally, they received an orientation regarding the study's objectives and its significance about their professional development. The selection of respondents was based on the assumption that they are actively managing and supervising schools in terms of organizational management and instructional supervision. They were expected to have a strong engagement with the curriculum implementation policy and pedagogical classroom activities, as well as the day-to-day management and execution of various school-based learning programs, projects, and activities designed to enhance early learners'

development within the framework of school-based management. The qualifications for participation in this study were rooted in the expectation that they had made significant contributions, extending beyond their primary roles in curriculum delivery, implementation, and governance, by actively participating in various educational activities. These contributions were typically discussed during school faculty meetings, group sessions, and committee meetings, all to improve the school environment and learners' educational experiences during the new regular learning system in the academic year 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various activities and advocacy-policy through school-based initiatives and in support of the school management and curriculum development delivery system.

2.3. Research Instrument—The instrument employed in this research study was meticulously crafted through a comprehensive review of existing literature and related studies. The researcher dedicated substantial effort to gathering and analyzing relevant literature, extracting key concepts that not only guided the instrument's development but also fortified its alignment with the designated strands. This thorough procedure contributed to creating a well-structured set of questionnaire items, thereby bolstering the overall validity of the instrument and mitigating potential challenges to its reliability. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts, each consisting of indicators of organizational management in terms of curriculum alignment and innovations, faculty and staff management, compliance and accreditation, technology integration, and inclusivity and diversity. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured instructional leadership in terms of instructional resources, instructional coaching and support, innovation and research, and assessment and evaluation. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or

validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence and generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.876, which means that 87.6 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs

(Pallant 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of organizational management. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation were provided below:

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The organizational management is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The organizational management is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The organizational management is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The organizational management is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The organizational management is not manifested

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1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The instructional leadership is not manifested

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The statements provide a clear overview of the sequential steps that define the data collection process. This approach is vital to ensure safety and mitigate any potential risks associated with gathering relevant data, especially given the current context of ongoing in-person interactions. Permission to conduct the study. In the second

week of December 2023, the researcher initiated the process of conceptualizing the content and objectives of the thesis proposal. Subsequently, she prepared various documents, including request letters, for the study. The research study strictly adhered to established ethical data collection procedures, as Creswell (2004) outlined, and followed the health protocols mandated by

the IATF's policy. As the research proposal was approved by the panel of members and the college dean in the last week of February to the first week of March 2024, the researcher composed and submitted a formal letter seeking permission to collect data and conduct the study within Davao City to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao City, following the proper channels. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. March 2024, the researcher prepared and created a Google sheet form for the online survey collection process, which was sent to the randomly selected respondents via email addresses and to respondents who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, a prepared hard copy of the survey sheets was given to each of them. Once done, the link was sent, and right away, responses were gen-

erated, thus, ready for sorting, analyzing, and interpreting. This activity was done right after the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to proceed with data gathering, which commenced on the third week of March 2024. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The preliminary analysis results were given to the thesis adviser during the second week of April 2024. For coaching and statistical treatment, the thesis adviser sought the assistance of the graduate school statistician to provide technical discussions in running the data and its interpretations and implications of the study sometime during the first week of April 2024 and further deepen the analysis to make more meaning with the interpretations of results during the second week of April 2024.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in statement problem number one (1) regarding the extent of organizational management and statement problem number two (2) regarding instructional leadership. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength / direction significant relationship between organizational management and instruc-

tional leadership. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address statement problem number 4, on the indicators of organizational management that significantly influence instructional leadership (Pallant, 2000) and (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the responses from the data gathered in tabular and textual form. It includes discussions of the results based on and integration with reviews of the related studies. This would be the basis for the decisions to be made given the hypothesis posed.

The Summary of Organizational Management

Table 1 shows a summary of organizational management. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: compliance and accreditation (3.46) is often manifested, while inclusivity and

diversity (3.28), technology integration (3.08), faculty and staff development (3.06), and curriculum alignment and innovation (2.78) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.13 denotes that the extent of organizational management is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Organizational Management

No	Organizational Management	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Curriculum Alignment	2.78	Moderately Extensive
2	Faculty And Staff Management	3.06	Moderately Extensive
3	Compliance And Accreditation	3.46	Extensive
4	Technology Integration	3.08	Moderately Extensive
5	Inclusivity And Diversity	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		3.13	Moderately Extensive

The extent of organizational management encompasses a broad and multifaceted domain that is pivotal to the success of any enterprise. At its core, organizational management involves the efficient coordination of resources, people, and processes to achieve predetermined goals and objectives. This discipline spans various dimensions, including strategic planning, human resource management, financial oversight, and operational efficiency (Laouni, 2023). Effective organizational management extends beyond the hierarchical structure and permeates the entire organizational ecosystem, influencing the culture, communication, and decision-making processes (Swart, et.al., 2022). Leaders must balance adaptability and stability, fostering an environment that can respond to dynamic external factors while maintaining internal cohesion. Madhakomala and Hanafi (2021) analyze the extent of organizational management and also delve into areas such as risk management, innovation, and continuous improvement, re-

The extent of organizational management encompasses a broad and multifaceted domain that is pivotal to the success of any enterprise. Kocasarac (2021) said that at its core, organizational management involves the efficient coordination of resources, people, and processes to achieve predetermined goals and objectives. This discipline spans various dimensions, in-

flecting the need for organizations to evolve in response to changing market conditions and technological advancements. Ultimately, Siperstein, et.al., (2022) explored the success of an organization is intricately tied to the effectiveness of its management, which must navigate the complexities of the modern business landscape with agility, foresight, and a commitment to sustainable growth.

The Summary of Instructional Supervision Table 2 shows the summary of instructional supervision. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators, which are as follows: instructional resources (3.10), assessment and evaluation (2.68), innovation and research (2.66) are sometimes manifested, while instructional coaching (2.54) is rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.74 denotes that extent of instructional supervision is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

cluding strategic planning, human resource management, financial oversight, and operational efficiency. Effective organizational management extends beyond the hierarchical structure and permeates throughout the entire organizational ecosystem, influencing the culture, communication, and decision-making processes (Leballo, et.al., 2021). Al Mahdi et al. (2023) explore fea-

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Instructional Supervision

No	Instructional Supervision	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Instructional Resources	3.10	Moderately Extensive
2	Instructional Coaching	2.54	Less Extensive
3	Innovation and Research	2.66	Moderately
4	Assessment and Evaluation	2.68	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean		2.74	Moderately Extensive

tures that it is crucial for leaders to strike a balance between adaptability and stability, fostering an environment that can respond to dynamic external factors while maintaining internal cohesion. The extent of organizational management also delves into areas such as risk management, innovation, and continuous improvement, reflecting the need for organizations to evolve in response to changing market conditions and technological advancements. Ultimately, the success of an organization is intricately tied to the effectiveness of its management, which must navigate the complexities of the modern business landscape with agility, foresight, and a commitment to sustainable growth.

Significant Relationship Between Organizational Management and Instructional Supervision

It can be depicted that Pearson’s Correlation generated a significant correlation between organizational management ($r=0.876$; $p<.000$) and instructional supervision. Table 3 flaunts the yielded results of the significant relationship between organizational management and instructional supervision. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between organizational management and instructional supervision must be rejected, for it provides empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Organizational Management and Instructional Supervision

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Instructional Supervision	0.876	<0.000	Significant	Reject H0

**Significant @ $p<0.05$.*

Polatcan, et.al., (2023) tested the relationship between organizational management and instructional supervision is fundamentally symbiotic, each influencing and complementing the other in the pursuit of educational excellence. Organizational management provides the overarching framework within which instructional supervision operates. It establishes the strategic vision, allocates resources, and sets the tone for

the organizational culture. The efficiency and effectiveness of instructional supervision are contingent upon the clarity and coherence of the organizational management structure. Conversely, instructional supervision plays a crucial role in realizing the organizational goals set by management. It ensures that teaching and learning practices align with the broader mission and vision of the institution. Instructional supervi-

sors collaborate with educators to implement organizational strategies, support professional development, and foster an environment conducive to effective teaching (Swart, et.al., 2022). Chan and Muthuveloo (2019) investigate the seamless integration of organizational management and instructional supervision results in a cohesive educational ecosystem where administrative decisions harmonize with instructional practices, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of education. This interdependence underscores the need for a collaborative and synergistic approach to educational leadership, where organizational management and instructional supervision work hand in hand to cultivate a

culture of continuous improvement and student success.

Domains of Organizational Management Significantly Influence Instructional Supervision

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis on the indicators of organizational management significantly influencing instructional supervision. Domains of organizational management in terms of curriculum alignment (0.000), faculty and staff development (0.001), compliance and accreditation (0.000) technology integration (0.000) and inclusivity and diversity (0.001) suggest significant influence over instructional supervision.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Organizational Management Significantly Influence Instructional Supervision

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decisions		
H (Intercept)	4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	4.145		
H (Intercept)	0.313	0.175	1.066	0.270	0.204		
Curriculum alignment	0.217	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.324	0.000	<i>*Reject H0</i>
Faculty and staff development	0.231	0.108	0.136	1.299	0.112	0.001	<i>*Reject H0</i>
Compliance accreditation	0.212	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.033	0.000	<i>*Reject H0</i>
Technology integration	0.252	0.097	0.210	2.098	0.035	0.001	<i>*Reject H0</i>
Inclusivity and diversity	0.237	0.107	0.102	1.010	0.312	0.000	<i>*Reject H0</i>
R²	0.878						
F-value	253.857						
p-value	<0.001						

**Significant @ p<0.05*

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.898 suggests that instructional supervision is explained by 89.8%. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value

(253.857) and F-statistic is significant p<.001, tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of organizational management. Transformational Leadership Theory is a concept in leadership studies that centers on the idea of

leaders who inspire and motivate their followers to achieve extraordinary results. Introduced by James MacGregor Burns and expanded by Bernard Bass, this theory emphasizes the transformative power of leaders who go beyond transactional exchanges (rewards and punishments) and engage with their teams on a deeper, more intrinsic level (Siperstein, et.al., 2022). Transformational leaders are known for their ability to articulate a compelling vision, set high expectations, and empower their followers to achieve goals beyond their self-interest. They lead by example, demonstrating commitment, enthusiasm, and ethical behavior. This leadership style fosters a sense of trust, loyalty, and mutual respect, leading to increased performance and satisfaction among followers. The Transformational Leadership Theory highlights the importance of inspiration, intellectual stimulation, individualized consideration, and idealized influence, all of which contribute to both personal and organizational growth (Madhakomala and Hanafi, 2021). Applying the Transformational Leadership Theory to the study of organizational management and instructional leadership of private school heads is highly relevant and effective. Private school heads who embody transformational leadership characteristics inspire and motivate their teams of educators and staff to achieve remarkable outcomes in both administrative and instructional domains. These leaders

set a compelling vision for their schools, aligning it with the educational mission and values, which helps create a shared sense of purpose among stakeholders. They engage in active support and development of their teaching staff, encouraging them to innovate and continuously improve their instructional methods. In terms of organizational management, private school heads following this theory tend to create a positive and collaborative school culture. They instill a sense of commitment, enthusiasm, and ethical conduct among their teams. This, in turn, leads to a more motivated and satisfied staff, which can have a direct impact on operational efficiency, resource allocation, and overall organizational performance. Transformational leaders are also more likely to build effective teams, delegate responsibility, and develop the leadership potential of their staff. In the realm of instructional leadership, private school heads who adopt transformational leadership traits foster an environment where teaching and learning flourish. They set high expectations for both students and educators and provide the necessary support and resources to meet those expectations. Their visionary approach encourages innovative teaching practices and a commitment to professional development, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes and a more enriched learning experience.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In this chapter, the outcomes, conclusions, and recommendations were delineated by the analyzed and discussed data, along with the implications drawn from the findings. The findings emanate from the articulated problem statement, while the conclusions are derived from the resultant findings. The recommendations, in turn, were formulated based on the implications gleaned from the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following were the findings of the study given the results in the presentation, analysis, and discussions. The extent of organizational management in terms of

compliance and accreditation (3.46) was often-times manifested, while inclusivity and diversity (3.28), technology integration (3.08), faculty and staff development (3.06), and curriculum

alignment and innovation (2.78), were sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.13 denotes that the extent of implementation of the disciplinary challenges index was sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of instructional supervision in terms of instructional resources (3.10), assessment and evaluation (2.68), and innovation and research (2.66) was sometimes manifested, while instructional coaching (2.54) was rarely manifested. The overall mean rating of 2.74 denotes that the extent of instructional supervision was sometimes manifested, thus moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between organizational management ($r=0.876$; $p<.000$) and instructional supervision. Domains of organizational management, such as curriculum alignment (0.000), faculty and staff development (0.001), compliance and accreditation (0.000), technology integration (0.000), and inclusivity and diversity (0.001), suggest significant influence over instructional supervision.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following were conclusions: The extent of organizational management in terms of compliance and accreditation was oftentimes manifested, while inclusivity and diversity, technology integration (3.08), faculty and staff development, and curriculum alignment and innovation are sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of instructional supervision in terms of instructional resources, assessment and evaluation, innovation, and research was sometimes manifested, while instructional coaching was rarely manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between organizational management and instructional supervision. Domains of organizational management, such as curriculum alignment, faculty and staff development, compliance and accreditation technology integration, and inclusivity and diversity, suggest significant

influence over instructional supervision.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisor. May prioritize the establishment and maintenance of a robust organizational management framework. This involves strategic planning, resource allocation, and fostering a supportive culture that encourages instructional excellence. Additionally, investing in ongoing professional development for instructional supervisors to enhance their leadership skills and ensure they are well-equipped to guide teachers effectively. School Principal. The study suggests a focus on creating a conducive environment for instructional supervision within the school. This includes fostering a collaborative culture among teachers, providing them opportunities for continuous professional development, and implementing transparent communication channels. Principals should also actively engage with instructional supervisors to seamlessly integrate organizational goals and instructional practices within the school setting. Teacher. They may be encouraged to embrace a culture of continuous improvement, participate in professional development opportunities, and seek feedback from instructional supervisors. Teachers must be proactive in staying updated on innovative teaching methods and incorporating them into their instructional strategies. Collaborative efforts among teachers and instructional supervisors can lead to a more dynamic and effective learning environment.

Future Researcher. The study recommends exploring the long-term impact of organizational management and instructional supervision on student outcomes. Additionally, investigating the implementation of technology in instructional supervision and its potential benefits or challenges could be a fruitful avenue for research. Examining the perspectives of various stakeholders, including students and parents, could provide a more comprehensive un-

derstanding of the holistic impact of organizational management and instructional supervision in the educational context.

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